

A Well-Traveled Mind for Professionals in Education

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Author Notes

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Abstract

Professionals in education who participate in short-term study abroad programs that include students reap many professional development and mental health benefits. As globalization reshapes the landscape of education, faculty-led international experiences have emerged not only as a means to enrich student learning but also as powerful catalysts for educator growth and well-being. Drawing on qualitative data, existing literature, and our extensive international backgrounds including study abroad leadership, we identify key areas in which educators benefit from these short-term programs—typically lasting one to two weeks—including increased intercultural competence and global identity, a lifestyle reappraisal including healthy habits and sources of deleterious stress, renewed pedagogical inspiration, strengthened student-faculty relationships, enhanced global perspectives on curriculum content, and possibilities for wider community engagement and service. The unifying theme and conclusion is that there is a need for institutional recognition of short-term study abroad participation as a legitimate form of professional development that warrants administrative support. These programs offer a unique blend of professional enrichment and mental health gains, reinforcing the value of global engagement for faculty development. Future policies should consider integrating these opportunities into broader faculty development frameworks and institutional models to promote both educational excellence and educator well-being in our era of globalization.

Keywords: study abroad, professional development, mental health, global identity, intercultural competence.

The Well-Traveled Mind for Professionals in Education

This paper explores the professional development and mental health benefits afforded professionals in education who participate in short-term study abroad programs that include students. As globalization, whereby “cultures influence one another and become more alike through trade, immigration, and the exchange of information and ideas” (Arnett, 2002, p. 774), reshapes the landscape of education, faculty-led international experiences have emerged not only as a means to enrich student learning but also as powerful catalysts for educator growth and well-being. Drawing on qualitative data, current literature, and our extensive international backgrounds including study abroad leadership, we identify key areas in which educators benefit from these short-term programs—typically lasting one to two weeks—including increased intercultural competence and global identity, renewed pedagogical inspiration, strengthened student-faculty relationships, and enhanced global perspectives on curriculum content. These are important professional development opportunities offered through study-abroad participation as a leader or group member. In addition to the academic and professional benefits, we highlight the mental health impacts for educators who engage in these programs, as well as challenges and risks.

Professional Development and Mental Health Benefits

Professional development and mental health are inextricably intertwined, so these will be discussed in the same section. Krantz (2024) suggests that how participants respond, both mentally and professionally, to a study-abroad experience is influenced by their flexibility, adventurous nature, and global awareness. We assert that these can be by-products of intercultural exposure in addition to preexisting traits. Our study-abroad experience as faculty leaders combined with the qualitative surveys we administered, corroborated that education

professionals who participated in our short-term study abroad programs reported a sense of personal rejuvenation, transformative awareness, reduced feelings of burnout, and a positive group dynamic, attributing these outcomes to the shift in routine, exposure to new cultural environments, and the opportunity for reflective practice away from institutional constraints. These experiences often foster deeper self-awareness and professional affirmation, contributing to sustained engagement in their teaching and administrative roles upon return (Milligan & Paquette, 2021; Paquette & Milligan, in review). Other professional development benefits include stronger resumes/curriculum vitae, greater intercultural competence and global understanding, and added value (in business parlance) to their respective organizations and reflected in annual work evaluations.

Additionally, our findings suggest that educator mental health and professional development are positively influenced by the shared nature of the experience with students, which fosters meaningful connections and community-building outside of traditional school settings. These changes can last long after the end of the study abroad program, and those participants can become catalysts and advocates for others' growth opportunities, thereby expanding their influence. While logistical and emotional challenges exist—such as pre-departure stress or cultural adjustment—the majority of participants found these challenges to be outweighed by the longer-term psychological and professional gains.

The best way to demonstrate the positive impact that study abroad opportunities can have on educators is to share thoughts from those who have participated, such as the following quotes from our Institutional Review Board approved survey:

What I liked best about the study abroad program was the way it pushed me outside of my comfort zone culturally, emotionally, and intellectually. Immersing myself in Costa Rica's culture allowed me to see the world through a different lens and appreciate the value of simplicity, community, and resilience. The opportunity to engage with local

people, especially those working in humanitarian roles, was incredibly inspiring. It reminded me why global education matters and how empathy and action can go hand in hand.

This experience has deeply impacted me on both a personal and professional level. Being immersed in Costa Rica's culture where community, sustainability, and compassion are deeply woven into daily life reminded me of the power of human connection and the value of intentional living. It reawakened a part of me that thrives on purpose-driven work and reinforced why I chose education as a lifelong calling.

Personally, it grounded me. Stepping away from my routine gave me clarity; I was reminded that success is not measure by test scores or titles, but by the lives we touch and the legacy we leave. Seeing children learn and grow with limited resources- but limitless love and determination reignited my own commitment to lead with heart.

This experience has had a profound personal impact on me. It reminded me to be more intentional about my own health and well-being—physically, mentally, and emotionally. Immersing myself in a culture that values balance, community, and simplicity helped me reflect on how important it is to slow down and prioritize self-care.

Challenges and Risks

While there are mental health benefits for professionals in education who participate in short-term study-abroad programs, there are also risks to well-being, many of which stem from participating students' mental health problems and insufficient resources to support faculty leaders and other associated professionals (Briscoe et al., 2020). For example, in a quantitative study, Barneche et al. (2025) administered the DASS-21 (Antony et al., 1998), a measure of depression, anxiety, and stress, to 102 education-abroad staff in Europe and found significant levels of all three. They “suggest that a holistic notion of mental health and well-being for university programs abroad must include a concern for, and scholarly attention to, international educators themselves” (p. 288). There is ample research focused on students, but little that is focused on faculty leaders or other education professionals involved in intercultural programs. This remains an area for further investigation.

There are other challenges and risks as well. Challenges include finding the time, often unpaid, to develop quality programs, recruit participants, and establish requisite cross-cultural professional and support networks. Risks involve inadequate resources and training to handle emergencies, such as accidents, mental health or medical crises, political turmoil, natural disasters, and litigation.

Conclusions and Implications

In conclusion, there is a need for greater institutional recognition of short-term study abroad participation as a legitimate form of professional development that warrants administrative support, including compensation. Short-term study abroad programs serve not only as high-impact practices for students but also as transformative experiences for educators, which has positive effects on themselves, their students, and colleagues. These programs can offer a unique blend of professional enrichment and mental health gains, reinforcing the value of global engagement for faculty development. Future policies should consider integrating these opportunities into broader faculty development frameworks and institutional models to promote both educational excellence and educator well-being in our era of globalization.

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